

STAGES OF TUTOR AND SUBJECT TEACHER DEVELOPMENT IN MODERN EDUCATION

Egamberdiyeva Iroda

Senior teacher of ASIFL

Department of tour guiding, intercultural communication
and translation studies

Urmonova Khurshida Kushakmirzaevna

Rakhmonova Mokhinur Ikromjon kizi

Faculty of english language and literature, group 342

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Annotation: The substantive and technological foundations of the organization of advanced training programs in accordance with the emergence of new pedagogical professions of a subject teacher, assistant, moderator, tutor, proofreader are outlined. The main elements of advanced training programs for teachers and innovative foundations for their implementation are presented. The effectiveness of the approach to designing programs for additional education of teachers from the standpoint of the functional division of pedagogical work at school is substantiated.

Keywords: additional education, professional development program, division of pedagogical labor, new pedagogical professions.

INTRODUCTION

Our opinion that the education reform has become more meaningful and purposeful is associated with the emergence of a number of legislative acts, initiatives, projects that are designed to regulate and guide the transformation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The improvement of the teaching profession must take place in part by changing the working methods of already practicing teachers, who must be able to adapt to new information and new requirements throughout their professional career. The educational system, if it wants to successfully reform, cannot wait for a new generation of teachers, it is necessary to invest in already practicing teachers, providing them with high-quality professional development, a well-thought-out career path, a variety of activities and awakening in them an interest in reform.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

So, the first step towards a qualitative change in the teaching staff of modern educational organizations and, above all, schools, should be the selection of young promising teachers who are potentially able to master new competencies. It is obvious that the next step should be advanced training or even retraining of these pedagogical workers. The problem of teacher retraining is a recognized

problem for all categories of teachers [3; 4]. Teachers constantly feel a high need to update their knowledge, while they are the least motivated to compete.

Now let's move on to the classical version of the division of labor along a conditional horizontal line. It can be called conditional, because it still implies a certain career growth, expressed in the professional, organizational and personal development of the teacher of the school. It must be said that the definition of new specific pedagogical professions in this aspect is accompanied by significant difficulties associated with the variety of approaches to the essence and content of pedagogical work. After all, the number of existing and newly offered professions is very large.

Often it turns out that newly formed professions or even entire professional groups fit well into the education system, but more often they serve only as an addition, an attempt to solve some isolated problems in education. At the same time, there is an obvious lack of any systematic idea of the division of labor in a particular educational system. There are practically no attempts to build a more or less coherent system of interaction between new professions or positions. It was this problem that we solved by offering our idea of the system of division of pedagogical labor at school.

We assume that the school will have four new pedagogical professions: subject teacher, tutor, moderator, and proofreader. Each of these professions is quite unique. In addition to the traditional subject teacher, it has its own functionality and the required set of competencies. At first glance, there is not much new in these professions; all of them, to one degree or another, have already been or are now involved in solving various pedagogical or organizational tasks at different levels of education. But once again, we would like to draw your attention to the fact that no one in the Uzbek education system has yet been able to bring them into a single harmonious working system. Let us briefly describe these professions and their place in the division of labor, their functionality and the main tasks solved in the school education system.

The next profession, which is used quite often now, especially in foreign educational systems, is a tutor. This is a specialist from among the teaching staff, who carries out the individualization of educational processes. Its main task is the formation and implementation of individual educational trajectories. Its main functions include:

- development of students' needs for self-education and self-development;
- assisting students in understanding their educational and professional prospects;

- designing a model of future activities, choosing ways and means to achieve the goal,
- monitoring of students' plans, their interests, inclinations, motives, readiness for professional self-determination.

CONCLUSION

Summing up this article, we can say that the material presented here is only an intermediate result of the implementation of the project "Teacher of the Future". And all teacher training programs are currently being finalized. However, their relevance in the field of education in Uzbekistan is already obvious.

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